

Assessing Emotional Intelligence from Textual Cues: A Natural Language Processing Approach to Emotional Quotient Prediction

¹Nikita Sinha,²Shaziya Islam

¹M Tech Computer Science & Engineering, Rungta College of Engineering and Technology,
Bhilai, Chhattisgarh, India

²Associate Professor, Rungta College of Engineering and Technology, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh,
India

¹nikitasinha.ms@gmail.com, ²shaziya.islam26@gmail.com

Corresponding author email address: nikitasinha.ms@gmail.com

ORCID id: 0009-0004-7418-3433

Abstract

Recent years have seen increased interest in applying AI methods to text data for EI and EQ assessment. Emotional intelligence (EI) and emotional quotient (EQ) are two key aspects of human thought and behavior that have an impact on decision-making, social interaction, and well-being. This paper aims to investigate the possibilities that comment analysis can offer in the automated discernment of emotional intelligence and quotient from textual data. By analyzing Twitter data, this paper tries to find out how exactly language is connected to EI, proposing a model to predict EQ scores based on textual data. The study implements an emotion classifier based on transformers, extracts emotion scores from each text sample, and maps these values to the five components of EI - self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. In the second part, the derivation of numerical EQ scores and qualitative feedback in the rule-based translator is automatically carried out with emotion profiles. We employ a pipeline for emotion identification or recognition that is mapped to five EI pillars: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence (EI); Emotional Quotient (EQ); sentiment analysis; natural language processing; emotion detection

1 Introduction

Emotional Intelligence (EI) and **Emotional Quotient (EQ)** have been in the limelight in research, especially in fields like psychology, human resource management, and education. Social media has become an essential aspect of everyday life, as the number of daily users has increased [1]. We can identify, comprehend, and control our own and others' emotions when we possess emotional intelligence (EI)[2] It has an enormous effect on how we interact with others, how we make decisions, and how we feel about ourselves in general [3], [4], [5]. Notably, emotionally intelligent systems are seen as more engaging, understanding, and trustworthy [6], which leads to identical advantages [7], [8].

Salovey and Mayer (1990) created and popularized the term "emotional intelligence," which refers to the capacity to track and comprehend our own emotions as well as those of others, distinguish between them, and use this knowledge to inform our decisions and behaviours. Since then, the quick advancements in psychology research have deepened our comprehension of emotional intelligence and allowed for the emergence of fresh viewpoints on the subject.[9], [10] and advancements over current standards [11], [12].The ability to identify, comprehend, and communicate emotions as well as control and regulate them is referred to as emotional intelligence[13].Traditionally, intelligence is measured through cognitive skills; rather, EI involves the control of one's thoughts and actions in different situations.

The method followed earlier for determining the EI and EQ uses self-report questionnaires and psychometric tests, which are usually biased and have limitations in accuracy. They tend to be time-consuming and intrusive and fail to fully capture the dynamic, complex nature of emotional intelligence in use in actual situations. There has been increased interest over the past few years in employing computational methods for analyzing text information and automatically estimating emotional intelligence, though. Sentiment analysis, the identification and extraction of emotional tone from text, offers a positive alternative for determining EI and EQ from text.

This paper focuses on techniques to estimate EI and EQ from text using pre-trained transformer models and a mapping framework grounded in psychology. The emotions identified in the text are brought into alignment with the five pillars of EI. The goal is to create a trustworthy and interpretable system that provides not only an EQ score but also feedback based on each pillar with respect to any input.

The findings of this research can be used in the development of more accessible and scalable measures of emotional intelligence with wider implications for both mental health and different fields like healthcare, organizations, and personal development. In this paper, we aim to bridge the gap between emotional intelligence and its practical use.

2 Literature Review

In this literaturereview section, we discussed the related works performed on emotion detection using NLP techniques for different fields like healthcare,sports,business and finance.

2.1 Techniques for Emotion Extraction

Basic human emotions have been studied by researchers in a number of widely recognized categories. The literature has numerous studies in the area of emotion identification. One of the most well-liked and extensively applied methods for identifying emotions is Ekman's emotion theory [24]. Writings, gestures, facial expressions, and speech can all be used to identify human emotions[14], [15].All of these factors have been the focus of emotion identification research[16]. The vast amount of research in a variety of disciplines, including psychology, social sciences, linguistics, human-computer interface (HCI), and communication, shows that it is possible to accurately identify emotions in text [17].

Table 1 Papers in which researchers categorize basic emotions.

Paper	Emotion class	Emotion Classification
[15]	8	Joy, agony, anxiety, astonishment, disgust, curiosity, embarrassment, and rage
[18]	8	Happiness, sadness, rage, fear, disgust, astonishment, acceptance, and expectation
[19]	6	Happiness, surprise, fear, rage, grief, and disgust
[20]	6	Joy, sorrow, rage, disgust, astonishment, and terror

2.1.1 Emotion Detection with conventional techniques

On the ISEAR dataset, Asghar et al. [21] classify emotions using a variety of machine learning methods (including SVM, Random Forest, XGboost, KNN, Logistic regression, SGD classifier, and Naive Bayesian) and choose the machine learning technique that yielded the best emotion identification results. The results demonstrate that, in comparison to other classifiers, logistic regression had the best performance. The main flaw is that the authors had restricted emotions and only used one dataset for their tests. of this study.

Suhasini et al. [21] used supervised machine learning techniques to identify the emotions in Twitter messages. Naive Bayes (NB) and K-nearest neighbor (KNN) algorithms were compared. The maximum accuracy was attained by the Naive Bayes (NB).

Bhagat et al. [21] use a hybrid strategy of Naive Bayes (NB) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) to categorize tweets into three classes: positive, negative, and neutral. They outperformed other methods, such as random forest, in terms of accuracy.

Two methods for categorizing Twitter texts into six distinct emotion categories—fear, sadness, happiness, disgust, rage, and surprise—are presented by Gand et al. [22]. Natural language processing was used in the first method, and two machine learning classifiers—the support vector machine and the decision tree classifier—were used in the second. The best performance has been demonstrated by the support vector machine classifier.

2.1.2 Deep Learning-Based Emotion Detection

Munika et al. [21] refine the pre-trained BERT model to carry out fine-grained sentiment analysis classification using the SST dataset. The accuracy of the aforementioned techniques was shown to be the highest when compared to the most popular deep learning models, including RNN, CNN, and LSTM.

Haryadi et al.[21]categorize text into seven emotions using long short-term memory (LSTM) and nested LSTM. Joy, love, fear, gratitude, wrath, sadness, and surprise are some of these feelings. They used SVM (Support Vector Machine) to compare their findings. The findings demonstrated that Nested LSTM provides the highest accuracy.

Adoma et al. [22] introduced a deep learning model for text emotion identification. The LSTM classification stage and the BERT fine-tuned training stage, which learned a word's context by considering other words, were the two stages of their model. They divided the text

into seven emotions using ISEAR. dataset. To determine the best, they were given an F-score of 0.73%.

Glove, parts of speech tagging, aspect embedding, gated recurrent unit, attention mechanism, and convolutional neural network (GPTA GRUAMCNN) were all merged in a model presented by Rani et al.[23].On the dataset of restaurant reviews, the accuracy was 98.29%.

Sindhu et al. [24]employ two LSTMs models, which are used for aspect extraction and sentiment detection. Different word embeddings are used to evaluate the model performance. Using the domain embedding as an embedding layer achieved better results. In aspect extraction, the accuracy was 91%, while in sentiment detection, the accuracy was 93%.

Polignano et al. [25] design a model based on the combination of BiLSTM, CNN, and self-attention. Therefore, the three-word embeddings,e.g., Google Word Embedding, Glove Embedding, and Fast Text output, were compared. The designed model for evaluation is based on the ISEAR, SemEval2018 Task1, and SemEval-2019 Task 3 datasets.

One example of this innovation is the BERT-CNN model, which combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) for text classification. The model achieves higher accuracy and efficiency in emotion recognition tasks by utilizing BERT for dynamic word semantic representation. With an accuracy of 94.7% with an F1-score of 94% on the SemEval 2019 Task 3 dataset and an accuracy of 75.8% with an F1-score of 76% on the ISEAR dataset, comparative studies show that it performs better than state-of-the-art baselines[26].

The study introduces a new approach in sentiment analysis with the aim of bettering the quality of content being presented to the users by eliminating emotionally injurious posts. The researchers obtained the user posts from the Twitter API and used an API for natural language understanding in order to extract and classify the emotions within the content. Joy, sadness, anger, fear, and disgust are the five fundamental emotional types that have been identified. To improve the accuracy of emotion detection, the study defined a comprehensive emotion array from more than 450 English words. The results show that this method greatly enhances the identification and categorization of negative emotional content, which helps to improve social media users' mental health safety.[27]

The machine-learning-based sentiment analysis method used in this study is based on extracting features from Term Frequency and Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) to enhance the quality of tweets by reducing noise. In the method, deep intelligent WordNet lemmatization is used to further optimize the quality of the text, too. Then, the emotion of a tweet is predicted by the Random Forest algorithm. Verifying with a battery of tests presented on publicly available datasets, the proposed method is demonstrably superior in multi-class emotion text data to other sentiment classification approaches [28].

3 Methodology

This section outlines the process followed for predicting Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Emotional Quotient (EQ) scores from Twitter data (textual). The steps of developing and evaluating a machine learning model are in this section. The methodology includes several key steps: data collection, data preprocessing, model testing, and evaluation. For ensuring the accuracy, reliability, and interpretability of the final predictive model, each of these steps is essential. The flowchart in fig. 2 shows how the process flows.

Figure 1 Flow chart of methodology.

3.1 DatasetCollection

In this section, we discuss how we gathered the data for this study from Twitter textual data. The Twitter dataset is collected from Kaggle to explore the relationship between language use in tweets and EI. These texts from Twitter express everyday feelings, thoughts, and

sentiments of people. This dataset is ideal for investigating emotional intelligence from tweets because it offers a variety of emotional expressions.

3.2 Data Preparation

Text pre-processing steps involve noise removal, tokenization, and normalization. Noise removal included lowercasing, punctuation, special characters, emojis, digits, stop words, HTML, hashtags, and URL removal. The main objective is to convert the raw text data (tweets) into structured information that can be used by machine learning models for emotional intelligence scoring.

The steps followed for data pre-processing are:

- **Tokenization:** Sentences are tokenized to break sentences into small tokens or words.
- **Removal of stop words:** Common words that do not convey emotions, such as "the", "an", "and", "is", etc., were eliminated. **NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit)** library is used for pre-defined list of stop words
- **TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency):** **TF-IDF Vectorizer** is used to convert the text data (tweets) into numerical form.

3.3 Emotion Detection (EI) and Emotional Intelligence mapping

To measure the emotional intelligence expressed in textual data generated by users (e.g., tweets), a two-step process was implemented:

1. Emotion detection using a transformer-based model, and
2. Mapping detected emotions to key Emotional Intelligence (EI) categories.

3.3.1 Emotion Detection

A pre-trained deep learning model—**j-hartmann/emotion-english-distilroberta-base**, which is the **DistilRoBERTa** architecture—is utilized for multi-class emotion classification. This model is available from Hugging Face's pipeline API for text classification and can detect fine-grained emotional subtleties in English-language text.

Every input text was sent to the model, which then generated an array of dictionary emotion labels (for example, joy, anger, sadness, fear, and surprise) and their respective confidence

scores. The scores denote either the intensity or likelihood of the emotion being possessed by the text. Thus, the output of the model was stored in a new dataset emotion_scores column, which was to be used for further processing.

3.3.2 Emotional Intelligence Mapping

The predicted emotions are mapped to five key pillars of emotional intelligence (EI) to score emotion. They are.

- **Self-awareness**
- **Self-regulation**
- **Motivation**
- **Empathy**
- **Social Skills**[29]

Every emotion influences particular EI dimensions either positively or negatively to specific EI dimensions. For example:

- Joy encourages self-awareness, motivation, and social skills.
- On the contrary, anger curtails self-regulation, empathy, and social skills.
- Sadness increases self-awareness and empathy but hampers motivation.
- Fear contributes to self-awareness and self-regulation.
- Surprise may boost empathy and social skills.

Each EI pillar was assigned a weighted contribution based on the detected emotional intensities. The normalized scores were then adjusted to be on a common 0-10 scale to preserve uniformity. An overall **Emotional Quotient (EQ)** score was then calculated by averaging the five EI pillar scores.

Based on the overall score, every individual and comment was classified into one of three EQ groups:

- **High EQ**(≥ 8) High levels of emotional awareness, regulation, and interpersonal skill.
- **Moderate EQ**(≥ 6): Reasonable emotional competence with room for improvement.
- **Low EQ** (< 6) means development is needed in measurements of emotional understanding and capability of social engagements and interaction.

This method enables an organized and scalable framework for assessing emotional intelligence using only text data.

4 Result

The following section deals with results of experiments carried out for assessing the effectiveness of machine learning models in predicting **Emotional Intelligence (EI)** and **Emotional Quotient (EQ)** from text data. The results are based on the analysis of tweets.

4.1 Dataset Summary

- Total tweets analyzed **61120**
- Average tweet length: **81.5 characters**

4.2 Emotional intelligence outcome

The average overall **EQ score** from the entire dataset: 3.23

This situates the corpus in the category of moderate emotional intelligence. The resultant feedback given was

"Overall, the dataset reflects moderate emotional intelligence, intelligence with a large room for improvement in emotional regulation and empathy."

4.3 Emotional Intelligence (EI) Wise Average

Table 2 Emotional Intelligence (EI) Score.

EI Pillar	Average Score
Self-awareness	5.07
Self-regulation	0.25
Motivation	2.27
Empathy	4.06
Social Skills	4.50

Table 2 shows the average score of five EI pillars[29]. The strongest area was **Self-awareness**, likely because of the presence of emotionally expressive language, if not by a

great deal of self-reflectiveness in the language used by those individuals. The lowest average score was in **Self-regulation**, possibly as a result of the content being emotionally reactive (for example, anger or frustration in the tweets). Below, figure 2 shows the average EI pillar score.

Figure 2 Average Emotional Intelligence (EI) Pillar Score.

4.4 Emotional Quotient (EQ) Score Distribution

The above distribution indicates that while a majority of users communicate with moderate emotional intelligence, a fair number have some opportunity to work toward accomplishing ameliorated emotional regulation and empathy. Figure 3 shows the overall distribution of EQ scores.

Figure 3 Distribution of EQ Score.

5 Discussion

This research would demonstrate the feasibility of assessing **emotional intelligence** through text using transformer-based **NLP** methods and psychology theory. Mapping the classified emotions to EI component pillars, we produced a scalable, explainable approximation of EQ. The primary advantage over black-box sentiment systems is that it informs about the specific pillars of EI rather than hiding information.

Nonetheless, a few *limitations* exist. Firstly, the mapping approach relies on predetermined rules that do not take some degrees of subtlety or sarcasm into account. Secondly, the emotion classifiers are contextual, meaning without a history of the conversation, the implication can easily be misconstrued. Thirdly, [29]Goleman's model presupposes a standard cultural and linguistic construct that may be far-fetched for all humankind.

Future areas of work should entail training supervised regression models with labeled study EI datasets (i.e., psychometric assessment sites), the integration of behavioral changes in how text is produced over time, and the extent to which we may consider multilingual or culturally adaptive mappings.

6 Conclusion

As our world is changing rapidly, digital communication is becoming more important than ever. From social media posts to customer feedback, the text expresses the people's opinions, feelings, decisions, and relations. This research determines how sentiment analysis and machine learning techniques have the potential to predict emotional intelligence (EI) and emotional quotient (EQ). Through the analysis of the vast amount of text data from Twitter, we have found a correlation between language use and emotional intelligence. A pre-trained deep learning model—**j-hartmann/emotion-english-distilroberta-base**, which is the **DistilRoBERTa** architecture—is utilized for multi-class emotion classification.

These findings propose that sentiment analysis and advanced machine learning models have been proven effective tools for assessing emotional intelligence, providing a scalable and non-intrusive method for measuring emotional intelligence. The ability to determine EI and EQ from text data opens a new door into understanding emotional dynamics, where emotion plays a key role in improving decision-making and interpersonal interactions and can be used

for applications in fields such as psychology, human resources, marketing, and customer service.

Despite the promising result, there are several challenges still to face. For instance, more sophisticated models are needed to deal with variations in emotional expression across cultures, as well as for even further refinement of the algorithm so it can be more effectively structured for multidimensionality of human emotional expression. Future researchers should concentrate on increasing datasets, enhancing model accuracy, and investigating the potential integration of multimodal data to further improve EI and EQ prediction.

In conclusion, the integration of sentiment analysis with machine learning provides a powerful approach to understanding and predicting emotional intelligence, setting the stage for more advanced tools capable of measuring and enhancing emotional awareness across a wide range of real-world domains.

7 Reference

- [1] J. Davila, R. Hershenberg, B. A. Feinstein, K. Gorman, V. Bhatia, and L. R. Starr, "Frequency and quality of social networking among young adults: Associations with depressive symptoms, rumination, and corumination.," *Psychol Pop Media Cult*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 72–86, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1037/a0027512.
- [2] P. Salovey and J. D. Mayer, "Emotional Intelligence," *Imagin Cogn Pers*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 185–211, Mar. 1990, doi: 10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK-6CDG.
- [3] N. S. Schutte *et al.*, "Emotional Intelligence and Interpersonal Relations," *J Soc Psychol*, vol. 141, no. 4, pp. 523–536, Aug. 2001, doi: 10.1080/00224540109600569.
- [4] N. S. Schutte, J. M. Malouff, M. Simunek, J. McKenley, and S. Hollander, "Characteristic emotional intelligence and emotional well-being," *Cogn Emot*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 769–785, Nov. 2002, doi: 10.1080/02699930143000482.
- [5] P. N. Lopes, M. A. Brackett, J. B. Nezlek, A. Schütz, I. Sellin, and P. Salovey, "Emotional Intelligence and Social Interaction," *Pers Soc Psychol Bull*, vol. 30, no. 8, pp. 1018–1034, Aug. 2004, doi: 10.1177/0146167204264762.
- [6] B. Reeves and C. Nass, "The Media Equation: How People Treat Computers, Television, and New Media Like Real People and Pla," 1996. [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/37705092>
- [7] V. K. Jain, S. Kumar, and S. L. Fernandes, "Extraction of emotions from multilingual text using intelligent text processing and computational linguistics," *J Comput Sci*, vol. 21, pp. 316–326, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jocs.2017.01.010.

- [8] L. Fan, M. Scheutz, M. Lohani, M. McCoy, and C. Stokes, "Do We Need Emotionally Intelligent Artificial Agents? First Results of Human Perceptions of Emotional Intelligence in Humans Compared to Robots," 2017, pp. 129–141. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-67401-8_15.
- [9] D. Schuller and B. W. Schuller, "The Age of Artificial Emotional Intelligence," *Computer (Long Beach Calif)*, vol. 51, no. 9, pp. 38–46, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1109/MC.2018.3620963.
- [10] J. D. Mayer, D. R. Caruso, and P. Salovey, "Emotional intelligence meets traditional standards for an intelligence," *Intelligence*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 267–298, Dec. 1999, doi: 10.1016/S0160-2896(99)00016-1.
- [11] S. E. Rivers, I. J. Handley-Miner, J. D. Mayer, and D. R. Caruso, "Emotional Intelligence," in *The Cambridge Handbook of Intelligence*, Cambridge University Press, 2019, pp. 709–735. doi: 10.1017/9781108770422.030.
- [12] P. Salovey and J. D. Mayer, "Emotional Intelligence," *Imagin Cogn Pers*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 185–211, Mar. 1990, doi: 10.2190/DUGG-P24E-52WK-6CDG.
- [13] Z. Cui and Y. Li, "The Relationship Between Proactive Behavior and Work-Family Conflict: A Moderated Mediation Model," *Front Psychol*, vol. 12, May 2021, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.657863.
- [14] S. Aman and S. Szpakowicz, "Identifying Expressions of Emotion in Text," in *Text, Speech and Dialogue*, Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 196–205. doi: 10.1007/978-3-540-74628-7_27.
- [15] V. K. Jain, S. Kumar, and S. L. Fernandes, "Extraction of emotions from multilingual text using intelligent text processing and computational linguistics," *J Comput Sci*, vol. 21, pp. 316–326, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jocs.2017.01.010.
- [16] R. Mihalcea and C. Strapparava, "Making computers laugh," in *Proceedings of the conference on Human Language Technology and Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing - HLT '05*, Morristown, NJ, USA: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2005, pp. 531–538. doi: 10.3115/1220575.1220642.
- [17] J. Lei, Y. Rao, Q. Li, X. Quan, and L. Wenying, "Towards building a social emotion detection system for online news," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 438–448, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.future.2013.09.024.
- [18] Robert Plutchik, *Emotion, a Psychoevolutionary Synthesis*. 1980.
- [19] A. Ortony, G. L. Clore, and A. Collins, *The Cognitive Structure of Emotions*. Cambridge University Press, 1988. doi: 10.1017/CBO9780511571299.
- [20] P. Ekman, "An argument for basic emotions," *CognEmot*, vol. 6, no. 3–4, pp. 169–200, May 1992, doi: 10.1080/02699939208411068.

- [21] D. Haryadi and G. Putra, "Emotion Detection in Text using Nested Long Short-Term Memory," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 10, no. 6, 2019, doi: 10.14569/IJACSA.2019.0100645.
- [22] A. F. Adoma, N.-M. Henry, and W. Chen, "Comparative Analyses of Bert, Roberta, Distilbert, and Xlnet for Text-Based Emotion Recognition," in *2020 17th International Computer Conference on Wavelet Active Media Technology and Information Processing (ICCWAMTIP)*, IEEE, Dec. 2020, pp. 117–121. doi: 10.1109/ICCWAMTIP51612.2020.9317379.
- [23] M. S. Rani and S. Subramanian, "Attention Mechanism with Gated Recurrent Unit Using Convolutional Neural Network for Aspect Level Opinion Mining," *Arab J Sci Eng*, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 6157–6169, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s13369-020-04497-4.
- [24] I. Sindhu, S. Muhammad Daudpota, K. Badar, M. Bakhtyar, J. Baber, and M. Nurunnabi, "Aspect-Based Opinion Mining on Student's Feedback for Faculty Teaching Performance Evaluation," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 108729–108741, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2928872.
- [25] M. Polignano, P. Basile, M. de Gemmis, and G. Semeraro, "A Comparison of Word-Embeddings in Emotion Detection from Text using BiLSTM, CNN and Self-Attention," in *Adjunct Publication of the 27th Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*, New York, NY, USA: ACM, Jun. 2019, pp. 63–68. doi: 10.1145/3314183.3324983.
- [26] A. R. Abas, I. Elhenawy, M. Zidan, and M. Othman, "BERT-CNN: A Deep Learning Model for Detecting Emotions from Text," *Computers, Materials & Continua*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 2943–2961, 2022, doi: 10.32604/cmc.2022.021671.
- [27] F. Benrouba and R. Boudour, "Emotional Sentiment Analysis of Social Media content for Mental Health Safety," Oct. 24, 2022. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-2170906/v1.
- [28] S. Saranya and G. Usha, "A Machine Learning-Based Technique with Intelligent WordNet Lemmatize for Twitter Sentiment Analysis," *Intelligent Automation and Soft Computing*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 339–352, 2023, doi: 10.32604/iasc.2023.031987.
- [29] "Emotional_Intelligence".